

HELENA: High-Efficiency Learning-based channel Estimation using dual Neural Attention

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Abstract—Accurate Channel Estimation (CE) is essential for high-performance Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM) systems such as 5G New Radio (5G-NR), especially under low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) conditions. This letter presents HELENA, a compact Deep Learning (DL) model that combines a lightweight convolutional backbone with two efficient attention mechanisms: a Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) block for local feature recalibration and a patch-wise Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) layer for capturing global dependencies. Compared to the most accurate baseline, Channel Estimator Vision Transformer (CEViT), HELENA reduces inference time by 45.5% (0.18 ms vs. 0.33 ms) while maintaining competitive accuracy (-16.87 dB vs. -17.41 dB). Compared to the fastest model, LS-augmented interpolated Deep Neural Network (LSiDNN), it improves accuracy by 13.2% (-16.87 dB vs. -14.91 dB) with only 12.5% higher inference time (0.18 ms vs. 0.16 ms). These results demonstrate HELENA’s effectiveness in jointly optimizing accuracy, efficiency, and latency for real-time deployment.

Index Terms—Channel Estimation, 5G-NR, OFDM, Deep Learning, Neural Attention, Neural Network Acceleration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate estimation of Channel State Information (CSI) is crucial for the effectiveness of OFDM-based wireless communication systems, such as 5G-NR, as it enables optimal resource allocation, beamforming, and adaptive modulation, all of which directly impact system capacity and reliability. In this context, CE refers to the process of acquiring or predicting CSI using received signals and known reference signals (e.g., pilot symbols). This process entails analyzing how the wireless channel affects transmitted signals using a variety of estimation algorithms. However, traditional methods like Least Squares (LS) and Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) suffer from high estimation error in noisy environments (e.g., LS) or incur substantial computational cost and rely on prior channel statistics (e.g., MMSE), limiting their suitability in low SNR or high-mobility scenarios.

To address these challenges, recent research has investigated both model-based and data-driven approaches for improving CE under realistic 5G and beyond conditions. Among model-based techniques, several recent methods have demonstrated competitive performance by leveraging signal structure and auxiliary information, such as pilot-free estimation for high-Doppler Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) scenarios [1] and sensing-assisted denoising of LS estimates [2]. In parallel, DL-based methods have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing CE by learning complex propagation patterns directly from data. These approaches lay the foundation for

Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native physical layer design [3] and the development of the next generation of intelligent radios [4], which is the focus of this letter.

Architectures such as ChannelNet [5], Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution (EDSR) [6], Attention mechanism and Residual Network (AttRNet) [7], and the more recent CEViT [8] have demonstrated superior estimation accuracy compared to conventional estimators. However, their high computational complexity limits their deployment in real-time 5G systems, which are constrained by strict latency, power, and hardware budgets [9], [10]. This has led to the development of lightweight architectures such as LSiDNN [11], which aim to balance accuracy with computational efficiency.

To address these limitations, we propose **High-Efficiency Learning-based channel Estimation using dual Neural Attention (HELENA)**, a lightweight hybrid DL architecture for pilot-based CE in OFDM systems without interpolation. It balances estimation accuracy and inference time by combining convolutional feature extraction with a dual-attention design: local features are extracted via 2D Convolutional (Conv2D) layers, global dependencies are captured through patch-wise MHSA, and salient channels are enhanced using a post-attention SE block. A linear reconstruction head and residual connection preserve structural information and support convergence, especially under high-SNR conditions. In this letter, we demonstrate that HELENA (i) achieves better accuracy–efficiency trade-offs than several state-of-the-art DL models, (ii) reveals that computational cost does not always correlate with inference time, and (iii) is fully reproducible, with open-source code and dataset made available¹.

The remainder of the letter is organized as follows. Section II provides the system model. Section III presents the proposed architecture. In Section IV, simulation results are presented. Finally, section V concludes this letter.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research considers the downlink Single Input Single Output (SISO) OFDM system model for 5G-NR. In an OFDM system, for the k_{th} time slot and the i_{th} subcarrier, the received signal, $Y_{i,k}$ is defined as follows.

$$Y_{i,k} = H_{i,k}X_{i,k} + Z_{i,k} \quad (1)$$

where $X_{i,k}$ is the transmitted OFDM signal and $Z_{i,k}$ represents Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with variance

¹https://github.com/miguelhdo/HELENA_Channel_Estimation

σ^2 . The considered OFDM subframe size is $N_S \times N_D$. The slot index k range is given as $[0, N_D - 1]$, and the subcarrier index i is given as $[0, N_S - 1]$. $H_{i,k}$ represents the (i, k) element of the channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_S \times N_D}$.

In practical OFDM systems, the channel matrix \mathbf{H} is unknown at the receiver and must be estimated from a limited set of pilot subcarriers, resulting in an underdetermined problem. Classical methods such as LS and MMSE [12] rely on pilot-based interpolation [13] to reconstruct the full channel, but each has drawbacks. While LS is computationally efficient, it is sensitive to noise. MMSE provides higher accuracy by using prior channel statistics but is computationally intensive and difficult to implement in dynamic environments. To address these limitations, recent approaches reformulate CE as a Super-resolution (SR) problem. The objective is to reconstruct an accurate channel response $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ from sparse pilot observations \mathbf{H}_p , modeled as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = f_{\Theta}(\mathbf{H}_{LR}), \quad (2)$$

where f_{Θ} represents a DL model parameterized by Θ , designed to learn complex mappings from a low-resolution estimate \mathbf{H}_{LR} to the full-resolution channel response. The low-resolution input can be directly obtained from raw pilot observations ($\mathbf{H}_{LR} = \mathbf{H}_p$) or constructed using traditional techniques such as LS combined with Linear Interpolation (LI), providing a less noisy but still incomplete representation of \mathbf{H} . This approach is analogous to SR techniques in image processing, where high-frequency details are recovered from degraded low-resolution inputs.

DL models such as ChannelNet [5] and EDSR [6] employ Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to learn spatial patterns in the channel matrix, achieving improved estimation accuracy over classical methods. However, their high model complexity and computational cost hinder real-time deployment. In contrast, the Super Resolution Convolutional Neural Network (SRCNN) architecture [9] offers faster inference due to its shallow structure but suffers from reduced accuracy.

To improve the accuracy–efficiency trade-off, AttRNet [7] incorporates the lightweight SE mechanism [14] to emphasize relevant features while maintaining a compact model size. The LSiDNN model [11] goes further by explicitly optimizing for low complexity, using a few dense layers to refine LS estimates, though this comes at the cost of reduced performance. On the other hand, CEViT [8] introduces a transformer-based architecture that leverages patch-wise self-attention to model long-range dependencies, achieving state-of-the-art accuracy, but at the expense of high computational complexity and inference latency. These trends highlight the need for a model that combines efficient local feature extraction, selective attention, and global context modeling, while maintaining low inference time, motivating the design of HELENA.

III. HELENA ARCHITECTURE

HELENA is a lightweight DL model for pilot-based CE in 5G-NR OFDM systems, designed to balance accuracy and inference time. It combines convolutional feature extraction with dual attention: patch-wise MHSA for long-range context and a low-cost SE block for channel-wise recalibration. The input is

Fig. 1. The proposed HELENA architecture.

a low-resolution LS-based estimate $\mathbf{H}_{LR} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_D \times 2}$, and the output is a full-resolution estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_D \times 2}$ over the time-frequency grid. The following subsection outlines the main architectural components and their design rationale.

A. Feature Extraction via Convolutional Layers

To extract local spatial features from \mathbf{H}_{LR} , the model uses two 2D convolutional layers with ReLU activations. The first convolutional layer applies a kernel of size $f_1 \times t_1$ and uses C_1 filters, producing an intermediate feature map $\mathbf{F}^{(1)}$. The second layer uses a kernel of size $f_2 \times t_2$ with C filters, resulting in $\mathbf{F}^{(2)}$. These layers have associated learnable weights $\mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{W}_2$ and biases $\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2$, respectively. A dropout layer is applied to improve generalization:

$$\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = \text{ReLU}(\text{Conv2D}_1(\mathbf{H}_{LR}; \mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{b}_1)) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{F}^{(2)} = \text{ReLU}(\text{Conv2D}_2(\mathbf{F}^{(1)}; \mathbf{W}_2, \mathbf{b}_2)) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{drop}} = \text{Dropout}(\mathbf{F}^{(2)}) \quad (5)$$

The output tensor $\mathbf{F}_{\text{drop}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_D \times C}$ is then partitioned into non-overlapping patches of height p , giving $N = N_S/p$ patches. This patching strategy enables localized spatial aggregation while reducing the sequence length, making the subsequent attention computation more efficient. Each patch is then flattened into a vector:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{patch}}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times N_D \times C}, \quad \mathbf{P}_i = \text{Flatten}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{patch}}^{(i)}) \quad (6)$$

B. Patch Embedding and Multi-Head Self-Attention

Each patch vector \mathbf{P}_i is projected into a shared d -dimensional embedding space using a learnable weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_e \in \mathbb{R}^{(pN_D C) \times d}$ and bias $\mathbf{b}_e \in \mathbb{R}^d$:

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{W}_e + \mathbf{b}_e, \quad \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d} \quad (7)$$

Each flattened and embedded patch vector \mathbf{Z}_i represents a localized region of the input and is referred to as a *token*, following the terminology of transformer-based architectures. These N tokens are stacked to form the input matrix $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$, where each row is a token embedding of dimension d . This token sequence is processed by the MHSA block to capture global context and long-range dependencies across the time-frequency grid. For each attention head j , the mechanism uses learnable projection matrices to map the input

into a query $\mathbf{Q}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^Q$, key $\mathbf{K}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^K$, and value $\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^V$, where $\mathbf{W}_j^Q, \mathbf{W}_j^K, \mathbf{W}_j^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_k}$ and d_k is the per-head dimension. The attention mechanism computes similarity between queries and keys to determine how much contextual information from each token (via the values) should be aggregated. The outputs from all h heads are concatenated and projected back using $\mathbf{W}^O \in \mathbb{R}^{hd_k \times d}$ follow by a layer normalization mechanism. For further details, we refer to the original Transformer formulation [15].

$$\mathbf{Q}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^Q, \quad \mathbf{K}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^K, \quad \mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{W}_j^V \quad (8)$$

$$\text{head}_j = \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}_j \mathbf{K}_j^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) \mathbf{V}_j \quad (9)$$

$$\text{MHSA}(\mathbf{Z}) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h) \mathbf{W}^O \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{att}} = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{Z} + \text{MHSA}(\mathbf{Z})) \quad (11)$$

C. Channel-wise Attention via Squeeze-and-Excitation

While MHSA captures long-range dependencies and aggregates contextual information across the full time-frequency grid, it treats all embedding channels equally during its output projection. However, not all channels (i.e., feature dimensions) contribute equally to the task of CE, e.g., some may carry more informative patterns depending on the propagation environment and pilot configuration.

To recalibrate channel importance, HELENA applies a lightweight SE block [14] across the token embeddings. First, a global descriptor $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is computed via average pooling:

$$\mathbf{s} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{Z}_{\text{att},i} \quad (12)$$

Then, two fully connected layers with weights $\mathbf{W}_{\text{se1}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d/r}$, $\mathbf{W}_{\text{se2}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d/r \times d}$ and nonlinearities (ReLU and sigmoid) produce the excitation vector $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{R}^d$:

$$\mathbf{e} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_{\text{se2}} \cdot \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{W}_{\text{se1}} \cdot \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{se1}}) + \mathbf{b}_{\text{se2}}) \quad (13)$$

The embeddings are rescaled accordingly:

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{scaled},i} = \mathbf{Z}_{\text{att},i} \odot \mathbf{e} \quad (14)$$

This post-attention recalibration step enables the network to focus on semantically meaningful representations by learning a global importance weighting over the embedding dimensions and selectively amplify the most relevant features, all with minimal computational overhead.

D. Reconstruction

Each scaled token is projected back to the original patch space using reconstruction weights $\mathbf{W}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times (pN_D \cdot 2)}$ and bias $\mathbf{b}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{pN_D \cdot 2}$:

$$\mathbf{P}'_i = \mathbf{Z}_{\text{scaled},i} \mathbf{W}_r + \mathbf{b}_r \quad (15)$$

The set of projected patch vectors $\{\mathbf{P}'_i\}_{i=1}^N$ is then reshaped and reassembled to form the output estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_D \times 2}$:

TABLE I
CHANNEL AND 5G-NR PARAMETERS FOR DATASET GENERATION

Parameter	Value/Description
Channel Profiles	TDL-A, TDL-B, TDL-C, TDL-D, TDL-E
Fading Distribution	Rayleigh
Number of Antennas (Tx, Rx)	1, 1
Carrier Configuration	51 RB, 30 kHz SCS, Normal CP
Sub-carriers Per Resource Block (RB)	12
Symbols Per Slot	14
Slots Per Subframe	2
Slots Per Frame	20
Frame Duration	10 ms
NFFT	1024
Transmission Direction	Downlink
PDSCH Configuration	PRB: 0-50, All symbols, Type A, 1 Layer
Modulation	16QAM
DM-RS Configuration	Ports: 0, Type A Position: 2 Length: 1, Config: 2
Delay Spread	1 - 300 ns
Doppler Shift	5 - 400 Hz
SNR	0 - 20 dB, steps of 2 dB
Sample Rate	30720000
Noise	AWGN
Interpolation	Linear
Data set shape	[11264, 612, 14, 2] = [# samples, SCS×RB, symbols per slot, real & imaginary components]

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \text{Reshape}(\{\mathbf{P}'_i\}_{i=1}^N) \quad (16)$$

Finally, a global residual connection [16] is included to improve convergence and ensure preservation of coarse structural information from the initial LS estimates:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H}_{\text{LR}} + \text{HELENA}(\mathbf{H}_{\text{LR}}) \quad (17)$$

The resulting architecture combines local and global feature learning with low complexity. Its dual attention mechanism, MHSA and SE, enables accurate reconstruction without interpolation or side information. As shown in Section IV, HELENA achieves high accuracy at low cost, confirming its suitability for real-time 5G-NR deployment.

IV. EVALUATION RESULTS

A. Dataset description

The dataset was generated using the MATLAB Data Synthesis for Channel Estimation in fifth-generation (5G) code². A summary of the parameters used to generate the dataset, such as the type of physical channel (e.g., Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH)), central frequency, Subcarrier Spacing (SCS), Cyclic Prefix (CP) type, number of RBs, code rate, and modulation, among others, is provided in Table I. Compared to the original code, some minor modifications were made. Specifically, the SNR values ranged between 0 and 20 dB, instead of 0 to 10 dB, and we generated 1024 samples for each SNR value, resulting in a total of 11,264 samples (11 SNR values × 1024 samples per value), with a split of 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing. The true labels are generated by assuming full CSI, while the model inputs are of two types: LS estimates on the pilot symbols, for HELENA and LSiDNN, and LI after the initial LS estimates, as utilized in ChannelNet, EDSR, AttRNet, and CEViT.

²<https://nl.mathworks.com/help/5g/ug/deep-learning-data-synthesis-for-5g-channel-estimation.html>

B. Baseline methods and models

We evaluate HELENA against seven DL-based baselines: SRCNN, ChannelNet [5], EDSR [6], AttRNet [7], LSiDNN [11], and CEViT [8], covering a range of architectures with different accuracy–complexity trade-offs. Additionally, we include two classical estimators: the LS method and a practical 5G-NR implementation. Both apply LS followed by linear interpolation (LI), while the practical version adds denoising and noise averaging³⁴.

Due to the lack of available implementations, all baselines were reimplemented from their original papers with adaptations for fair comparison and efficient deployment. ChannelNet uses 32 Denoising Convolutional Neural Network (DnCNN) filters (vs. 64) to reduce complexity without loss of accuracy. EDSR is adapted with 32 filters and 16 residual blocks to jointly process IQ data via 2D-CNN, outperforming ChannelNet [6]. AttRNet uses the AttResNet-Conv variant with 32 filters, offering better accuracy and lower cost than our EDSR setup. For LSiDNN, we evaluate both the original 48-neuron and a 1024-neuron variant to match our dataset’s higher input size. In CEViT, the inverse patch embedding is implemented with a `Conv2DTranspose` layer for TensorRT compatibility without affecting accuracy. All models use `padding='same'` and exclude upsampling. We also assess HELENA-MHSA (no SE) to isolate the effect of dual attention on performance.

Experiments were conducted on the GPULab testbed⁵ using 4 vCPUs, 64GB RAM, and the NVIDIA Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) Tesla V100-SXM3 (32 GB). The system ran CUDA12.2, TensorFlow2.15, and TensorRT8.6.1. Models were trained using the Adam optimizer and Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss with a batch size of 64, early stopping (patience 50), and a learning rate schedule starting at 0.01 with 0.8 decay every 40 stagnant epochs (min 1×10^{-5}). Validation loss guided checkpointing. Inference time was averaged over 100 single-sample runs on the test set. Results refer to TensorRT-optimized models, as non-optimized versions showed similar accuracy but are unsuitable for deployment [9].

C. Design decisions and parameter selection in HELENA

The parameters of HELENA were chosen based on the structural characteristics of the input data and validated empirically to optimize the trade-offs between estimation accuracy, inference time, and model complexity. The convolutional layers use 12×2 and 6×7 kernels to exploit the time-frequency layout of the OFDM grid while remaining lightweight. A patch size of 12 along the frequency axis yields 51 tokens, matching the 51 RBs in the dataset. Each token is embedded into a 64-dimensional space, which offers sufficient capacity for expressive representation while avoiding overfitting or excessive compute. The MHSA block uses 4 heads, allowing parallel modeling of diverse attention patterns without excessive overhead while maintaining high accuracy.

Fig. 2. MSE as a function of SNR for various CE methods

A reduction ratio of 4 in the SE block avoids overly aggressive bottlenecks, enabling meaningful channel-wise recalibration at low cost. Dropout (rate 0.1) and residual connections further enhance generalization and convergence.

D. Accuracy

Fig. 2 presents the Normalized Mean Squared Error (NMSE) (in dB) across a range of SNR values for all evaluated estimators. As expected, DL-based models outperform classical CE approaches such as LS and the practical estimator by a large margin. Among them, CEViT achieves the best average NMSE at -17.41 dB, consistent with its original report in [8]. HELENA follows closely with an NMSE of -16.87 dB, but unlike CEViT, HELENA operates without requiring explicit SNR, Doppler, or latency inputs, nor does it rely on a separate interpolation step, making it a more streamlined design.

When compared to other lightweight architectures, HELENA achieves significant accuracy gains: 5.9% over EDSR (-15.88 dB), 4.8% over AttRNet (-16.07 dB), and 7.3% over ChannelNet (-15.64 dB). The classical SRCNN baseline reaches only -14.03 dB, with HELENA improving accuracy by 18.3%. Finally, the HELENA variant without the SE block experiences a 5.5% drop in accuracy, falling below AttRNet-Conv. This highlights the effectiveness of the dual attention design, where the inclusion of the SE block yields measurable performance gains with negligible added computational cost.

E. Computational cost vs. Inference time

To meet the stringent latency requirements of 5G-NR, CE, equalization, and decoding must be completed within the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) deadline, which permits up to three Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs) (0.5 ms per TTI for 30kHz SCS) [10], so roughly a TTI for CE. As shown in Table II, all evaluated models satisfy this 0.5 ms constraint. Notably, HELENA achieves an excellent trade-off, delivering the second-best accuracy, only 3.2% lower than

³<https://www.mathworks.com/help/5g/ref/nrchannelestimate.html>

⁴https://github.com/srsran/srsRAN_Project/blob/main/lib/phy/upper/signal_processors/port_channel_estimator_average_impl.cpp

⁵<https://doc.ilabt.imec.be/ilabt/gpulab/>

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF NMSE (dB), FLOPS, AND INFERENCE TIME USING AS
BASELINE HELENA. LOWER VALUES ARE BETTER.

Model	Params (M)	FLOPS ($\times 10^9$)	NMSE (dB)		Inf. Time (ms)	
			Value	Δ	Value	Δ
SRCNN	0.014	0.24	-14.03	18.3%	0.13	-29.0%
ChannelNet	0.18	3.11	-15.64	7.3%	0.29	56.0%
EDSR	0.30	5.25	-15.88	5.9%	0.36	96.5%
AttRNet-Conv	0.075	1.29	-16.07	4.8%	0.30	65.6%
LSiDNN 48	1.66	0.003	-13.69	18.8%	0.08	-56.0%
LSiDNN 1024	35.11	0.07	-14.91	11.6%	0.16	-12.9%
CE-ViT	0.88	0.05	-17.41	-3.2%	0.33	80.0%
HELENA MHSA	0.11	0.08	-15.94	5.5%	0.17	-6.0%
HELENA	0.11	0.08	-16.87	—	0.18	—

CEViT, while offering the lowest inference time among the top three models. Specifically, CEViT and AttRNet are 83% (0.33ms vs. 0.18ms) and 67% (0.30ms vs. 0.18ms) slower than HELENA, respectively. Moreover, HELENA operates at only 36% of the 0.5 ms latency budget, ensuring compatibility with real-time 5G-NR constraints.

Inference times measured on the Tesla V100 show that runtime performance does not scale proportionally with Floating-point operations per second (FLOPS). For instance, although HELENA uses 66.7% fewer FLOPS than SRCNN (0.08×10^9 vs. 0.24×10^9), its inference time is 38.5% higher (0.18 ms vs. 0.13 ms). Similarly, AttRNet and EDSR perform 16 times and 65 times more operations than HELENA, yet their inference times increase by only 65.6% (0.30 ms) and 96.5% (0.36 ms), respectively. ChannelNet is also slower by 37.9%, despite requiring 39 times more operations (3.11×10^9).

Parameter count also shows limited correlation with runtime or estimation performance. For example, HELENA reaches -16.87 dB NMSE with 0.11 million parameters, fewer than ChannelNet (0.18 million) and much fewer than LSiDNN-1024 (35.11 million), while achieving better accuracy and lower inference time. CEViT achieves the lowest NMSE (-17.41 dB) using 0.88 million parameters, eight times more than HELENA, but it runs slower despite requiring fewer FLOPS. These comparisons highlight the need to jointly consider FLOPS, parameter size, and inference time when optimizing models for real-time CE. These results indicate that FLOPS or parameter size alone do not accurately predict inference time, and direct timing measurements are necessary when optimizing and evaluating models for real-time CE in real deployments.

V. CONCLUSION

This letter presented HELENA, a hybrid DL-based model for efficient and accurate pilot-based CE in OFDM systems. HELENA combines shallow convolutional layers with dual attention—patch-wise MHSA and channel-wise SE to balance estimation accuracy, model complexity, and inference time. Experimental results demonstrate that HELENA achieves near state-of-the-art accuracy with significantly fewer parameters and competitive runtime, making it well suited for real-time applications in latency-constrained systems such as 5G-NR. The observed weak correlation between FLOPS, parameter count, and inference time highlights the need for holistic evaluation criteria when designing DL-based CE models. Future

work will extend HELENA to higher mobility scenarios, new waveform types, and deployment on hardware platforms such as FPGA and edge AI accelerators.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research has been funded by the 6G-TWIN project, which has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101136314.

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